

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Tl(I)-3-NITRO SALICYLATES

Method	30°			35°			40°		
	log K_1	log K_2	log B_2	log K_1	log K_2	log B_2	log K_1	log K_2	log B_2
HI	7.91	5.12	13.03	7.32	4.57	11.89	6.56	4.70	11.26
LP	7.90	5.11	13.01	7.25	4.57	11.82	6.53	4.65	11.18
PC	7.87	5.01	12.88	7.31	4.45	11.76	6.66	4.38	11.04
LS	7.80	5.01	12.81	7.27	4.26	11.53	6.69	4.25	10.94
Average	7.87	5.05	12.81	7.29	4.46	11.75	6.60	4.60	11.10

mentioned methods and are recorded in Table 1. The values of formation constants are concentration stability constants. Although the values obtained

average value is recorded in Table 2. The values of ΔS were then evaluated from the relation

$$\Delta S = \Delta H - \Delta F/T$$

and are recorded in Table 2.

Fig. 1. Formation Curves of Tl(I)-3-Nitro Salicylates

○ 30°C; △ 35°C; □ 40°C.

by the method of least-square would be more acceptable, it may be seen that these values as determined by other methods are also representative values of the formation constants.

Perusal of Table 1 shows that the ratio $\log K_1/K_2$ is positive and that the separation factor between first and second formation constants is well within the expected range. A bigger difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ and a high value of $\log K_1/K_2$ is because of possible steric hindrance on the linking of the second ligand molecule expected for Tl(I) ion.

The values of change in free energy (ΔF), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) for the complexation reaction have been determined applying the standard equations. The values of ΔH is determined by temperature co-efficient method as well as from the isobar.

$$\frac{d \ln K_n}{dT} = \Delta H/RT^2$$

which can be written as

$$\frac{d(\log K_n)}{d(1/T)} = \Delta H/4.57.$$

The values of $\log K_n$ were plotted as a function of $1/T$ and the gradient of the tangent was equated to $-\Delta H/4.57$ and thus ΔH was found in K.cal., the

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR Tl(I)-3-NITRO SALICYLATES

Temp.	$-\Delta F_1$ (K.cal./mole)	$-\Delta F_2$ (K.cal./mole)	$-\Delta H_1$ (K.cal./mole)	$-\Delta H_2$ (K.cal./mole)	$-\Delta S_1$ (e.u.)	$-\Delta S_2$ (e.u.)
30°	14.77	10.98			46.57	14.55
35°	14.22	10.34	28.88	55.09	47.60	14.53
40°	13.96	9.53			47.60	14.55

The formation of Tl(I)-3NSA is a spontaneous process which is evident from free energy value. The negative values of ΔH ensures that the reaction is exothermic and metal-ligand bond is stronger than the ligand-solvent bond. The negative values of ΔS indicate that the products are more ordered than the reactants.

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Studies in Oxadiazoles. Part III. Synthesis of Some Basic N-(5-Aryl-1,3,4-Oxadiazol-2-yl) Acetamides

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BASIC acetamides, in which amido-H has been substituted with aromatic¹ or heterocyclic² moieties have been synthesised in large number as potential local anaesthetics. Of these Lidocaine¹

is the most outstanding and satisfactory local anaesthetic³. Several basic N-(2-thenyl/furfuryl)-acetamides have been patented as analgesic and antispasmodics⁴.

In view of above it was presumed that the title compounds might have enhanced biological activities, as the oxadiazole moiety is associated with many interesting biological properties, such as, analgesic^{5,10} hypoglycemic⁶, bactericidal⁷⁻⁹ and antipyretic¹⁰ etc.

With this object, basic N-oxadiazolylacetamides have been prepared, by condensing¹¹ secondary amines with various 2-chloroacetamido oxadiazoles and the latter compounds were obtained by the method of Bhargava and Singh¹². The required 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles were prepared according to the method of Gibson.¹³

Basic N-(5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)acetamides (II). To a solution of 2-chloroacetamido oxadiazole (I) (0.5 M) in absolute ethanol (30 ml) was added an ethanolic solution of appropriate secondary amine (0.1 M) and the mixture refluxed for 5 hr. Excess of the amine and ethanol were removed and the residue was washed successively with sodium carbonate solution and water. The product was recrystallised from benzene. The basic acetamides(II) thus prepared are recorded in Table 2.

IR spectra

The IR spectra (in nujol mull) of 2-chloroacetamido oxadiazoles(I) and basic N-oxadiazolylacetamides(II), reveal characteristic absorption bands for -C=O, -C=C- and -C-O-C- groups in the expected regions

TABLE 1—5-ARYL-2-CHLOROACETAMIDO-1, 3, 4- OXADIAZOLES (I)

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis %		Significant bands (cm ⁻¹) in IR spectra			
					Found	Calcd.	-C=O	-C=C-	-C-O-C-	
1.	H	209	70	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂ Cl	C	50.34	50.53	1740	1458	1280
					H	3.29	3.37			
					N	17.40	17.68			
2.	o-Chloro	161	62	C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₂	C	44.08	44.12	1744	1470	1262
					H	2.46	2.57			
					N	15.41	15.44			
3.	p-Methoxy	173	74	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₃ Cl	C	49.02	49.35	1742	1465	1262
					H	3.70	3.74			
					N	15.62	15.70			
4.	p-Dimethylamino	170	61	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	C	51.12	51.34	1715	1460	1223
					H	4.68	4.63			
					N	20.11	19.96			
5.	p-Nitro	175	64	C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₄ O ₄ Cl	C	42.22	42.48	1738	1460	1230
					H	2.43	2.48			
					N	20.14	19.82			

Experimental

2-Amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles were prepared by oxidative cyclisation of aldehyde semicarbazones (0.05 M) with bromine (0.1 M) and anhydrous sodium acetate (16 g) in glacial acetic acid.

5-Aryl-2-Chloroacetamido-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (I). A solution of chloroacetyl chloride (0.06 M) in benzene (50 ml) was treated with a benzene solution of the 2-amino oxadiazole (0.06 M) and refluxed for 1-2 hr. Benzene was removed, the residue washed successively with sodium bicarbonate solution and water and finally recrystallised from ethanol. The compounds thus prepared are recorded in Table 1.

(vide Table 1 and 2). The -C=O stretching frequency in (I) has appeared at a slightly higher value (55-96 cm⁻¹) as compared with the similar absorption in (II); this may be attributed to the greater electron attracting property of α -chloro group than -NR'R'' group.

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NOTES

TABLE 2—BASIS N-(5-ARYL-1, 3, 4-OXADIAZOL-2-YL) ACETAMIDES (II)

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis %		Significant bands (cm ⁻¹) in IR spectra		
					Found	Calcd.	-C=O	-C=C-	-C-O-C-
<i>R' = R'' = Ethyl</i>									
1.	H	238	70	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	C 61.15 H 6.40	61.31 6.57	1650	1460 1600	1160 1285
2.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	168	61	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	C 54.66 H 5.58	54.46 5.51	1655	1458 1580	1175 1300
3.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	235	74	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃	C 59.42 H 6.41	59.21 6.58	1658	1502 1607	1190 1262
4.	<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino	195	57	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₂	C 60.36 H 7.34	60.57 7.26	1670	1525 1612	1185 1308
5.	<i>p</i> -Nitro	205	55	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₄	C 52.91 H 5.36	52.66 5.33	1683	1518 1608	1162 1284
<i>R' = R'' = Phenyl</i>									
6.	H	231	78	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	C 71.65 H 4.74	71.35 4.86	1648	1464 1607	1164 1284
7.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	205	65	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	C 65.45 H 4.08	65.27 4.20	1648	1458 1590	1160 1258
8.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	237	70	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃	C 69.21 H 4.89	69.00 5.00	1657	1500 1608	1178 1259
9.	<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino	247	72	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₂	C 70.01 H 5.44	69.73 5.57	1675	1522 1582	1160 1265
10.	<i>p</i> -Nitro	244	68	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₄	C 63.42 H 4.28	63.61 4.10	1595	1510 1582	1160 1265
<i>R' R'' = Piperidin.</i>									
11.	H	202	65	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	C 62.61 H 6.16	62.94 6.29	1655	1495 1598	1160 1282
12.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	159	58	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	C 56.38 H 5.18	56.16 5.30	1652	1502 1608	1170 1290
13.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	168	70	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃	C 60.43 H 6.24	60.76 6.33	1660	1518 1608	1196 1268
14.	<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino	207	65	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₂	C 61.85 H 7.15	62.01 6.99	1670	1522 1607	1184 1305
15.	<i>p</i> -Nitro	190	62	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₄	C 54.52 H 4.96	54.38 5.14	1680	1515 1608	1158 1284

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Monomethylglyoxime Complexes of Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) Chlorides

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α -DIOXIMES like dimethylglyoxime, α -furyl dioxime etc. are well known analytical reagents. The literature survey shows that not much work has been done on the use of unsymmetrical glyoximes in preparation of metal complexes. The present communication deals with preparation of solid coordination complexes of monomethylglyoxime with copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II) chlorides and their characterisation by elemental analysis, I.R. and electronic absorption spectra and magnetic susceptibility.

Experimental

The metal salts used were of analytical reagent grade. The ligand and the metal complexes were prepared by the following methods: Monomethylglyoxime (MMG) was prepared by the method given in the literature¹, m.p. 154° (Found: N, 27.42%; Calcd. for $C_3H_6O_2N_2$: N, 27.50%). Solid metal complexes were prepared by refluxing alcoholic solution of metal chlorides and the ligand in 1:2 molar ratio. In preparing Co(II) complex, it was necessary to raise the pH of the solution to 8.0–8.5 pH with alcoholic ammonia solution. The complexes were purified by washing with alcohol and ether and dried over anhydrous $CaCl_2$.

The complexes were decomposed with HCl and metal ion contents were estimated using standard EDTA solution. Nitrogen was estimated by micro-Kjeldahl's method. The chloride content in copper and cobalt complexes was estimated as silver chloride. Molar conductances were measured on LKB-3216 conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were done at TIFR, Bombay in the temperature range 300°K to 80°K on Gouy balance using mercury(II) tetrathioocyanato cobaltate(II) as a calibrant

Diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constants. IR absorption spectra were recorded in nujol mull with Perkin-Elmer infracord 137-E. Diffuse reflectance, U.V. and visible spectra were measured on Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The experimental data on electronic spectra, magnetic susceptibility and solution molar conductivity of the complexes are set out in Table 1.

Copper(II) complex:

The elemental analysis of the green coloured crystalline compound conforms to the formula $Cu(C_3H_6O_2N_2)Cl_2$. The molar conductance in methanol shows the complex to be a non-electrolyte. The observed magnetic moment 1.87 B.M. for Cu(II) at room temperature is very nearly the same as the reported value 1.85 B.M. at 300°K for the copper complex of dimethylglyoxime² which is known to be square planar. The diffuse reflectance and solution electronic spectral bands (Table 1) suggest square planar symmetry for the complex³. The intense band observed in 40,000 cm^{-1} region is probably due to charge transfer transition.

Nickel(II) complex:

The scarlet-red coloured complex having the formula $Ni(C_3H_6O_2N_2)_2$ arrived at from elemental analysis, appears to be a non-electrolyte from its conductivity in nitromethane. The diamagnetic nature of the complex favours a square planar

TABLE I
ELECTRONIC ABSORPTION SPECTRA, MAGNETIC DATA AND CONDUCTANCE VALUES OF Cu(II), Ni(II)
AND Co(II) COMPLEXES WITH MONOMETHYLGlyOXIME

Compound	Medium	Absorption maxima cm^{-1} and molar extinction coefficients (ϵ)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Λ_M mhos
Cu MMG Cl_2	Diffuse reflectance	25,000; 22,730–19,230; 16,000–13,700.	1.87	48.04 (methanol)
	Chloroform	40,320–40,000(6785); 20,700(70) 13,610–13,520(60)		
Ni(MMG) ₂	Diffuse reflectance	24,390; 22,220–21,550	Diamagnetic	4.78 (nitromethane)
	Chloroform	37,880–37,310(5633); 30,300–29,850(1287); 27,030–26,320(62); 22,730(260); 19,800(70).		
Co(MMG) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ ·Cl ₂	Diffuse reflectance Methanol	24,390; 16,000 39,370 (15,880); 22,00sh, 16,000sh; 12820(28); 10,420(11).	1.49	199.80(methanol)

MMG = monomethylglyoxime; sh = shoulder.